

Working Group on Reforming Academic Career Assessment

List of tools from case studies

ANECA

- New accreditation criteria:
 - In [English](#)
- [Table annexed to the resolution on criteria resolution](#) (in Spanish)
- [FAQ](#) (in Spanish)
- [Narrative CV template](#) (in Spanish)
- [Participation platform](#) (in Spanish)
- [New Code of Ethics](#) (in Spanish, published in the Official State Gazette)

CLACSO-FOLEC

- [A new research assessment towards a socially relevant science in Latin America and the Caribbean](#)

CoARA

- The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment includes [a toolbox with practical tools to support the implementation of the 10 commitments](#) (see Annex 4 of the Agreement). This toolbox is subject to continuous development.

DORA

- [Reformscape](#). Reformscape is an online interactive database of openly available responsible research assessment policies, practices, and processes at academic institutions. This database is designed to [grow via community submissions](#) and includes a suite of supporting materials to help users navigate the database, including an introductory [brief](#) and [video](#), a [how-to guide](#), and an [FAQ](#).
- The [case study repository](#), created in collaboration with SPARC Europe and the European University Association, is a collection of detailed case studies of responsible research assessment reform across a wide range of types of organisations.

- [Five things to consider to optimize, evaluate and iterate on the use of narrative CVs.](#) This quick reference tip sheet outlines ideas for research funders to optimize, evaluate and iterate on the use of narrative CVs for funding decisions.
- [Building Blocks for Impact.](#) Building Blocks for Impact is a one-pager that outlines and illustrates the wide variety of academic achievements and outcomes that could be considered “impactful”.
- [Debiasing Committee Composition and Deliberative Processes.](#) Debiasing Committee Composition and Deliberative Processes is a one-page brief that identifies strategies for including more perspectives and reducing biases in the evaluation processes for hiring, promotion, tenure, and funding decisions.
- [Ideas for Action.](#) Ideas for Action outlines five common myths about research evaluation to help universities better understand barriers to change and provides analogous examples to illustrate how these myths exist inside and outside of academia.
- [Unintended Cognitive and Systems Biases.](#) Unintended Cognitive and Systems Biases identifies seven personal biases that can influence hiring, promotion, and tenure decisions.
- [SPACE to evolve academic assessment: A rubric for analyzing institutional conditions and progress indicators.](#)
- [Balanced, broad, responsible: A practical guide for research evaluators.](#) Balanced, broad, responsible: A practical guide for research evaluators is a short, informative video that is accompanied by a one-page brief.

EU-CHARTER

- Brochures: <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/useful-information/brochures>.
- The “HR Excellence in Research” award gives public recognition to research institutions that have made commitments and progress in aligning their human resource policies with the principles set out in the Charter. HRS4R Technical guidelines for institutions: <https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/jobs/hrs4r>.
- The EU Competence Framework for Researchers (ResearchComp) is promoting transversal skills development for researchers and careers in all sectors of the society, including academia, businesses and industry, public administration. ResearchComp:

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2023-04/ec_rtd_research-competence-presentation.pdf

FINLAND

- [The researcher's curriculum vitae \(CV\)](#)
- [Policy for open scholarship](#)
- [Self-evaluation tool for culture of open scholarship services](#)
- [Guidelines for the Responsible Conduct of Research](#)
- [User guide for the Publication Forum classification](#)
- [Research.fi](#)
- [Researchers' views on diversity of career assessment criteria in Finland: a survey report](#)

NETHERLANDS

- This [Dialogue toolkit](#) is a practical step-by-step plan which could help institutions to create dialogue with academics. It sums up the essentials for organising a dialogue, including suggestions for session formats and a guide for discussion moderators. An introduction to this toolkit could be found [here](#).
- A [double interview](#) on the development of career paths
- Five [good practices](#) in developing career paths

NORWAY

- The [NOR-CAM](#) framework is in itself a toolbox or toolkit, meaning that all tools should not be used at the same time.

OR4

- The OR4 toolkit consists of a [maturity framework and self-assessment tool](#), which can be used to support institutional maturity assessment, planning and progress, and an integrated implementation guide, which will provide in-depth practical guidance across all areas of implementation described in the maturity framework, and will include case studies from participating institutions and resources they have developed to support implementation and practice.

- OR4 will also publish a searchable knowledgebase of relevant initiatives and resources that institutions can draw on to support activity to implement recognition and reward for open research.
- The OR4 survey of 60 UK institutions' policies and practices in relation to responsible research assessment and open research was undertaken in 2023 and the [report of the survey findings](#) was published in March 2024. This provides a baseline overview of the current UK landscape, against which national progress will be assessed when the survey is re-run in 2026.

UKRI

- Traffic light system at the end of the [plan](#)

YUFE4Postdocs

- [YUFE4Postdocs Structured CV Template](#)